

Elderly	main model	20.3	75	1.062 (1.047-1.077)	1.026 (1.020-1.032)	1.026 (1.020-1.032)	1.004 (1.000-1.007)	1.004 (1.000-1.007)	1.004 (1.000-1.007)	1.004 (1.000-1.007)	0.999 (0.996-1.001)	0.999 (0.996-1.001)	0.999 (0.996-1.001)	0.999 (0.996-1.001)	0.999 (0.996-1.001)
	lag 5	20.3	75	1.067 (1.055-1.080)	1.027 (1.021-1.033)	1.027 (1.021-1.033)	1.003 (1.000-1.006)	1.003 (1.000-1.006)	1.003 (1.000-1.006)	1.003 (1.000-1.006)					
	lag 3	20.3	75	1.066 (1.055-1.077)	1.025 (1.018-1.032)	1.025 (1.018-1.032)	1.007 (1.001-1.014)	1.007 (1.001-1.014)							
	lag 1	20.2	75	1.061 (1.051-1.071)	1.030 (1.025-1.035)	1.030 (1.025-1.035)									

- **Health impact assessment method**

The mortality attributable to temperatures above the temperature threshold was calculated daily, and then summed:

$$M_{ij} = \sum_{i=1}^N DM_{ij} \left(\frac{RR_{ij} - 1}{RR_{ij}} \right)$$

$$\text{where } RR_{ij} = e^{(b_j \Delta T_{ij})}$$

M_{ij} corresponds to the total estimated number of temperature-related deaths per year calculated on each day, i , for each region, j , for the total number of days in the whole period, N . DM_{ij} corresponds to the daily CVD mortality in region j on day i . RR_{ij} represents the calculated relative risk of mortality for heat effects for day i , in region j and b_j is the slope of the exposure-risk relationship for heat for each region, which reflects the change in CVD mortality per 1°C change in daily mean temperature above the regional threshold for heat.

Table S2. Number of CVD deaths (AN) attributed and fraction of CVD mortality (AF) attributed to temperatures above temperature threshold and CVD mortality rate.

			Baseline	SSP2-4.5				SSP5-8.5			
			1999-2018	2020-2039	2040-2059	2060-2079	2080-2099	2020-2039	2040-2059	2060-2079	2080-2099
REMTTh	General Population	AN	2326.23	3379.31	3959.83	4534.10	4989.97	3550.05	4681.18	5989.99	7662.79
		AF (%)	9.73	14.13	16.56	18.96	20.86	14.84	19.57	25.04	32.04
		Mortality Rate	382.49	555.64	651.09	745.52	820.47	583.72	769.70	984.90	1259.95
	Elderly	AN	2302.30	3313.66	3868.68	4413.70	4845.52	3476.86	4552.81	5788.45	7358.03
		AF (%)	10.67	15.36	17.93	20.46	22.46	16.11	21.10	26.83	34.10
		Mortality Rate	1769.31	2546.54	2973.07	3391.92	3723.77	2671.96	3498.82	4448.41	5654.63
Regional Unit of Xanthi	General Population N. Xanthi	AN	516.80	761.99	898.27	1033.38	1141.74	802.07	1068.48	1381.31	1781.67
		AF (%)	9.07	13.38	15.77	18.15	20.05	14.08	18.76	24.25	31.28
		Mortality Rate	464.65	685.11	807.63	929.11	1026.54	721.15	960.68	1241.94	1601.90
	Elderly	AN	246.81	363.57	427.64	491.37	542.55	382.43	508.17	655.13	843.43
		AF (%)	9.54	14.05	16.52	18.99	20.96	14.78	19.64	25.31	32.59
		Mortality Rate	1440.32	2121.70	2495.55	2867.45	3166.14	2231.75	2965.53	3823.12	4921.97

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Figure S2. Spatial risk maps of heat-related CVD mortality for the general population in the Municipality of Xanthi for the baseline period (1999-2020) and the period 2020-2099 under the SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios.

Figure S3. Spatial risk maps of heat-related CVD mortality for the elderly in the Municipality of Xanthi for the baseline period (1999-2020) and the period 2020-2099 under the SSP2-4.5 scenario.

b. Fluvial Flooding workflow Supplementary Material

Figure S4. Inundation depth of Kosynthos River for 100, 200 and 500 extreme event return periods

Figure S5. Daily timeseries of river discharges (m³/s) based on various different GCM-RCM climate model combinations for the period 1991-2006

Figure S6. Monthly mean river discharges (m^3/s) for the study catchment for different GCM-RCM combinations and time periods

Figure S7. Extreme river discharges (m^3/s) for the study catchment for different GCM-RCM combinations and for 10-year and 50-year return periods

Figure S8. Relative change in extreme river discharges for the study catchment for different GCM-RCM combinations and for 10-year and 50-year return periods

Figure S9. Flood and associated damages maps over Xanthi for RCP 8.5 and extreme event return period 10 years

Figure S10. Flood and associated damages maps over Xanthi for RCP 8.5 and extreme event return period 50 years

Figure S11. Flood and associated damages maps over Xanthi for RCP 8.5 and extreme event return period 100 years

Figure S12. Flood and associated damages maps over Xanthi for RCP 8.5 and extreme event return period 200 years

Displaced population for the river flood event with 10-year return period
(Population statistics based on estimate for the year 2025)

Figure S13. Displaced population for the river flood event (with an inundation depth greater than 1 meter) with a 10-year return period

Displaced population for the river flood event with 500-year return period
(Population statistics based on estimate for the year 2025)

Figure S14. Displaced population for the river flood event (with an inundation depth greater than 1 meter) with a 500-year return period

c. Wildfires workflow Supplementary Material

The supplementary figures presented here provide a comprehensive view of the Fire Weather Index (FWI) hazard and risk assessment workflow. The first set of figures illustrates the historical hazard assessment, showing key metrics such as FWI exceedance probabilities for selected thresholds and their spatial and temporal variability. Building on these historical results, the second set of figures documents the application of the FWI response model, which links variations in key climate drivers to changes in hazard indicators, allowing an evaluation of model behaviour and sensitivity. A third set of figures extends the analysis to climate projections, showing projected changes in FWI exceedance probabilities under different future scenarios and thresholds. Finally, the fourth set of figures presents the population risk assessment, integrating the projected hazard indicators with exposure data to characterize potential impacts on human populations. Together, these supplementary figures ensure continuity across the workflow, enhance transparency, and support reproducibility without overloading the main text.

Figure S15 Selected Grid Points for EL51

Figure S16 Day of Year Statistics of FWI in EL51 (1981-2010)

Figure S17 FWI Probability of exceedance in EL51 (1981-2010)

Figure S18 Number of days in fire Season in EL51

Figure S19 FWI Exceedance Probability for Selected Thresholds

Figure S20 Probability of exceeding an FWI of 50 in EL51

Figure S21 Change in probability of exceeding an FWI of 50 in EL51

Figure S22 Average fire season length (FWI > 30.2 in EL51)

Figure S23 Mean temperature (top) and precipitation (bottom) change under RCP8.5

Figure S24 Projected temperature and Precipitation change under RCP8.5

Figure S25 EL51/RCP8.5 response probability of exceeding FWI

Figure S26 The diagram shows the evolution of the response variable (hazard indicator) for the region. The central line follows the median response of the ensemble at each timestep, while the shaded areas highlight the 25-75 percentile (dark) and total (light) ranges of the model ensemble.

Figure S27 EL51/RCP8.5 response probability of exceeding FWI in a year

Figure S28 Total Population EL51 under SSP5 scenario

Figure S29 Hazard affected population

Table S3 Hazard assessment – Data overview (FWI)

Hazard data	Vulnerability data	Exposure data	Impact metrics / Risk output
<p>We calculate the daily Fire Weather Index (FWI) using historical and future weather data straight from the Copernicus Climate Data Store (the tourism fire danger indicators dataset). This covers the period 1985–2005 historically, and future projections under different climate scenarios (RCP4.5, RCP8.5 etc.). The main ingredients are everyday weather at noon: temperature, rainfall, wind speed, humidity. We also use the fuel moisture codes (FFMC, DMC, DC) and fire behavior indices (ISI, BUI). For the “what-if” part, we take real ERA5 weather from 1981–2010 and artificially change temperature (+0 to +5 °C) and rainfall (–40% to +60%). Data comes from ERA5 Zarr files or GRIB files (Zenodo DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10458186) and EURO-CORDEX climate</p>	<p>In the pure hazard part we don’t model vulnerability in detail, we just see how sensitive things would be to different FWI levels (basically how easily forests, fields or buildings would burn depending on the fuel/land type). When we move to risk we bring in: percentage of population living in Wildland-Urban Interface (from EFFIS), fraction of protected areas, ecosystem irreplaceability score, and an index of how expensive it would be to restore the area after a fire. Xanthi version: We try to use as much local land-use information as possible (e.g. the typical forests around Thrace).</p>	<p>We define the area using official Eurostat NUTS shapefiles for Xanthi (EL51), add a small buffer so we don’t miss edge effects. We filter only burnable areas (using ESA-CCI land cover – we exclude anything non-flammable like water, bare rock, urban concrete etc.). Future climate comes from EURO-CORDEX projections (decade by decade until 2099), cropped exactly to the Xanthi shape. Xanthi version: We layer in population density from EFFIS + future population grids under different socio-economic scenarios (SSPs).</p>	<p>We fit a Gumbel distribution to the yearly maximum FWI values → this gives us the Probability of Exceedance (PE) – e.g. chance that FWI goes above 60 can jump from ~20% to ~64% depending on how much warmer/wetter it gets. Return Period = 100 / PE (e.g. once every 31 years for FWI=69). Fire Season Length: number of days per year the FWI is above half the 20-year extreme value (on average ~87 days in the reference period). Standard danger classes: Low <11.2 → Moderate → High → Very High → Extreme → Very Extreme (>70). Xanthi version: We make local seasonal FWI maps, show exceedance</p>

models. For Xanthi specifically: We zoom in using the NUTS code EL51 (East Macedonia & Thrace), pick a sensible bounding box around the area, and average over the regional grid points.			probabilities, and always include the uncertainty range from the model ensemble (median + 25th–75th percentiles).
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Table S4 Risk assessment

Hazard data	Vulnerability data	Exposure data	Impact metrics / Risk output
Core is still the FWI, but only calculated/considered over burnable land (filtered with ESA-CCI land cover). We usually look at the summer season (June–September). Future projections come from Copernicus under different RCPs, using several climate models together..	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population density (people/km² from EFFIS) • % of population living in Wildland-Urban Interface (where houses meet forest) • % of protected areas covered • How unique/irreplaceable the local ecosystems are • How expensive it would be to restore the landscape after a big fire <p>All these factors are considered to increase risk when they are higher. Xanthi version: We pay special attention to the typical urban-forest edges we have in Thrace.</p>	<p>Future population grids (2020–2100) under different SSP scenarios, resampled to match our hazard grid. Burnable vegetation % from EFFIS is our main exposure proxy. We clip everything to the exact Xanthi boundaries.</p> <p>Xanthi version: Wherever possible we bring in higher-resolution local population data, focusing especially on communities close to forests.</p>	<p>We calculate affected population only in places where the hazard is high enough (e.g. PE \geq30%), and show the full uncertainty range. We create a simple Fire Danger Index by combining FWI and burnable area percentage (both normalized 0–1, equal weight). We also make Pareto risk maps that highlight the areas that are worst/best in terms of multi-criteria risk. Finally, we show how the number of people potentially affected evolves from 2030 to 2090 under different climate & society scenarios.</p>

Table S5 Fine-tuning to local context

<i>Hazard data</i>	<i>Vulnerability data</i>	<i>Exposure data</i>	<i>Impact metrics / Risk output</i>
<p>We start from the same perturbed FWI statistics (temperature & precipitation changes), based on CMIP6-informed data (Zenodo DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10458186).</p>	<p>Mostly atmospheric, but we add: • Local land cover details (e.g. pine, oak, maquis typical in Xanthi) • Burnable materials from EFFIS/ESA-CCI • Population in Wildland-Urban Interface • Protected areas (Natura 2000 sites around Xanthi) • Restoration cost index Local fine-tuning: We feed in our own newly created land-cover maps made with remote sensing – much better detail than the global datasets.</p>	<p>Local fine-tuning: We create brand new land-cover maps using remote sensing – this dramatically improves how accurately we know which areas can actually burn and where people & assets really are exposed.</p>	<p>Xanthi fine-tuning: We customise the danger thresholds according to local experience (e.g. maybe FWI>60 is the real local “extreme” threshold). We are careful not to over-extrapolate far outside our data range.</p>